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Features of Future Teachers's Training in Order to Work in a Bilingual Educational Environment

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Abstract

The recognizing of the priority of the educational space unity in the Russian Federation, the protection and traditions' development of the people of Russia require the comprehensive implementation of the multicultural potential of the country's regions as a source of preservation and transmission of historical and cultural heritage to the younger generation, starting from preschool age. Bilingual education, as one of the conditions for the implementation of a multicultural approach to education, is aimed at supporting the positive social orientation of the modern people consciousness: the need to study their native languages, the history of their native land and native culture. The relevance of the problem is due to the need of considering the conditions for the training of teachers for their professional activities in the bilingual environment of the multicultural educational space of the Komi Republic, where the Russian-Komi bilingual population is dominant. In the main professional educational programs for an enlarged group of specialties and areas of training (hereinafter referred to as EGSA) "Education and Pedagogical Sciences", disciplines that are aimed at building the professional competence of future teachers in a bilingual educational environment cannot always be found. In the Komi Republic schools, the teaching is carried out in Russian, and the curriculum provides the Komi language training, both as native and non-native.

The purpose of the article is to reveal the effective pedagogical conditions (educational, methodical, information-methodical and research-methodical) to the formation of the future teachers' ethnocultural competence for their professional activities in the bilingual environment of the Komi Republic. The leading research methods for this problem are analysis and generalization of normative, educational and methodical documentation and psychological and pedagogical literature, as well as a method of a design. The pedagogical conditions presented in the article will allow forming the ethnocultural competence of future teachers who will carry out their professional activities in the bilingual educational environment of the school.

Keywords: bilingual educational environment, multicultural educational space, educational and methodological conditions, information and methodological conditions, research and methodological conditions, professional competencies, ethnocultural competence

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Introduction

One of the conditions for the implementation of a multicultural approach to education is bilingual education, aimed at supporting the younger generation awareness of the need to learn their native language, the history of their native land and native culture. In the territory of the Komi Republic, Russian-Komi bilingualism is dominant, so there was a need to create conditions for the teachers training for their professional activities in the bilingual environment of a multicultural educational space. In the main educational professional programs 44.03.01 Pedagogical education (Ministry of Education and Science of the Russian Federation, 2018) and 44.03.02 Psychological and pedagogical education (Ministry of Education and Science of the Russian Federation, 2015), the disciplines aimed at building the professional competence of future teachers in a bilingual educational environment cannot always be found. In the schools of the Komi Republic, the teaching is carried out in Russian, and the curriculum provides the Komi language training, both as native and non-native.

The analysis of the federal state educational standard of higher education (hereinafter referred to as the FSES of HE) in the profile of training 44.03.02 Psychological and pedagogical education showed that university students should have a general professional competence aimed at developing the ability to conduct professional activities in a multicultural environment, taking into account the peculiarities of socio-cultural development.

The federal state educational standard of higher education 3++ (hereinafter FSES HE 3++) in the profile of training 44.03.01 Pedagogical education states that university students should have groups of universal competencies aimed at intercultural interaction.

The Federal State Educational Standard of Primary General Education (hereinafter referred to as the FSES PGE) (Ministry of Education and Science of the Russian Federation, 2009) is aimed at ensuring: “the preservation and development of the cultural diversity and linguistic heritage of the multinational people of the Russian Federation, the right to learn the native language, the possibility of obtaining primary general education in the native language, mastery of spiritual values and culture of the multinational people of Russia ...”. The FSES PGE is also based on a system-activity approach, which involves: “the upbringing and development of personality qualities that meet the requirements of the information society ...; based on the tolerance, dialogue of cultures and respect of the multinational, multicultural and multiconfessional composition of the Russian society ... ”.

Having examined the foreign authors' existing definitions of the concept of "bilingualism" (Weinreich, 1972) and domestic authors (Vereshchagin, 1969; Filin, 1972; Desheriev, 1976; Zalevskaya & Medvedeva, 2002; Andreeva, 2009; Pozdnyakova, 2011; Zavodnitskaya, 2015; Khamraeva, 2015; Rezunova, 2019), we came to the conclusion that bilingualism is a fluency in two languages, one of which dominates the other. Since the Russian Federation is a multinational country and the state language is Russian, there is a need to take into account "Russian-native" bilingualism when organizing the educational process both at school and in a university in order to implement a personality-oriented approach.

A great contribution to solving the problems of teaching Russian-Komi and Komi-Russian bilinguals was made by scientists and methodologists such as Igushev (1988), Sazhina (1990), Prokusheva & Polyakova (2010), Terentyeva et al. (2016), Yakubiv et al. (2016). These researchers studied the problems of improving the process of teaching the Russian and Komi languages, both as native and non-native. These authors have developed educational and methodological complexes in the Russian and Komi languages for schools of the Komi Republic.

Ethnocultural competence is disclosed in the works of such authors as Morozov (2011), Gaysina et al. (2015), Poshtareva (2005), etc.

Purpose and objectives of the study

The purpose of the study: to reveal effective pedagogical conditions (educational, methodological, information-methodical and research-methodical) of the formation of future teachers' ethnocultural competence to carry out professional activities in the bilingual environment of the Komi Republic.

Experimental base of research was the Department of Primary Education, Institute of Pedagogy and Psychology, FSBEI HE "Pitirim Sorokin SSU", MEI Secondary School s. Storozhevsk, MBEI "Pazhginskaya Secondary School", MAEI Secondary School No. 38, Syktyvkar, MAEI Secondary School No. 36, Syktyvkar, MAEI Secondary School No. 24 Syktyvkar, MBEI "Mokhcha Secondary School named after the Hero of the Soviet Union A.G. Khatanzevsky", MBEI Secondary School s. Loima. 205 teachers were covered: 159 of them were primary school teachers, 32 were teachers of the Komi language and 14 were teachers of the department of primary education.

Literature review

Development stage. Purpose: the implementation of the pedagogical conditions for the formation of future teachers' ethnocultural competence in the educational and extracurricular educational process of the university. (see Table 1).

Table 1 Project Implementation Stages

Stages of the study	Stage content
Ascertaining stage	
1. Theoretical analysis of normative and psychological-pedagogical literature, aimed at highlighting the problem.	The formulation of the original idea and purpose of the study. Drawing up a list of necessary and existing specialists necessary for the implementation of the project.
	The performing of the issue state review on the topic of the research in normative and psychological-pedagogical literature and practice; the analysis of the material collected.
2. The empirical study of the activities of the teachers engaged in their professional activities in the bilingual educational space and implementing elements of ethnocultural education.	Review of the status of the issue on the topic of the research in practice. Analysis of the collected factual material. Stating the hypothesis.
Development stage	
The implementation of the pedagogical conditions for the formation of future teachers' ethnocultural competence in the educational and extracurricular educational process of a university	The development and implementation of the pedagogical conditions in the subject matter of taught disciplines and in extracurricular activities for the formation of future teachers ethnocultural competence at a university when realizing the educational programs 44.03.02 Psychological and pedagogical education (FSES HE) and 44.03.01 Pedagogical education (FSES HE 3 ++.)

Based on the practice-oriented approach, pedagogical conditions have been created aimed at the formation of ethnocultural competence of future teachers who are able to carry out professional activities in a bilingual environment using the elements of ethnocultural education of the Komi Republic.

Ascertaining stage.

The purpose of this stage is a theoretical analysis of the existing methodological approaches and the empirical study of the teachers' activities in the field of implementation of the elements of ethnocultural education of the Komi Republic.

Let us consider the possibility of training a graduate in the undergraduate program in the profile 44.03.01 Pedagogical education. In accordance with the Federal state educational standard 3 ++, a bachelor's graduate must have universal competence "to be able to perceive the intercultural diversity of society in socio-historical, ethical and philosophical contexts" and a general cultural competence "to be capable of carrying out spiritual and moral education of students on the basis of basic national values".

In order to prepare future teachers for professional activities in the bilingual environment of the Republic of Komi, it is necessary to form ethnocultural competence.

"Ethnocultural competence is a personality trait, expressed in the presence of a set of objective ideas and knowledge about a particular ethnic culture, realized through skills, abilities and behavioral models that promote effective interethnic understanding and interaction".

Ethnocultural competence as an objective-subjective phenomenon has the following set of contents (see Figure 1):

Figure 1. Comparison of FSES of different levels of training and the content of the concept of “ethnocultural competence”

Methodology

The leading research methods of this problem are the methods of analysis and generalization of normative, educational and psychological documentation and psychological and pedagogical literature, as well as the design method.

Results

In the context of the discussed issue of the theory and practice of the students' ethnocultural competence formation, we will describe as an example the experience of the department of primary education of the Institute of Pedagogy and Psychology of "Pitirim Sorokin SSU".

For the formation of ethnocultural competence of future teachers in the context of bilingualism and the implementation of the requirements of the Federal State Educational Standards of Higher Education, Federal State Educational Standards of Higher Education (3++), Federal State Educational Standards of Higher Education, teachers of the department implement interconnected groups of conditions when organizing the educational process: educational methodological, informational methodological, research methodological.

I. Educational and methodological conditions:

1. The use of pedagogical technologies in bilingual education, which allows to organize social activities and social interaction of students with the outside world in a multi-ethnic educational environment, to express a personal attitude to it and to regulate the nature of relations with various objects of ethnosocial and cultural reality. Bilingual education is based on such pedagogical technologies as the technologies of the design (the creation of animated films based on oral folklore materials, the creation of didactic and handouts in the subject areas), game technologies (for example, the business game "The teacher council on the topic: "The adaptation of schoolchildren", role-playing games "Traveling around the Komi Republic", "A letter to a friend", "The interview with the birch-barker", etc.), informational technologies (the creation of electronic catalogs, tests, sites, blogs, etc.), communicative technologies (for example, the designing of classroom hours on the topics: "Learning to be friends", "Friendly handshakes", "Komi mu on your palm" and testing them on focus groups during classes), health-saving technologies (the organizing and conducting by students healthy days at the institute using mobile Komi national games, the compiling of set of cards of physical breaks with ethnocultural content and testing them in the focus group during classes, designing a system of measures to create a health-saving environment in the framework of methodological disciplines of the educational institution main educational program, the annual photo contest in the virtual

environment “Sports and national traditions of my family”, etc.). In addition to the above-mentioned technologies, there are technologies aimed at the formation of ethnocultural competence of future teachers, one of which is the quest technology. It allows to study objects of ethnocultural heritage, work with local history material, organize excursions, etc.

2. The content of the bilingual education implies extensive opportunities for the implementation of intersubject integration, which makes it possible to show the culture of different peoples through works of literature, music and painting. In order to prepare future teachers for work in a bilingual environment, such disciplines as “Ethnocultural education of primary schoolchildren”, “Children's literature of the Komi Republic”, “Methods of teaching technology in elementary grades”, “Methods of teaching fine art in primary school” implemented by the department of primary education are included in the main professional educational programs, and the work of bilingual students is organized as part of scientific and extracurricular activities, which involves the use of the Komi language and the culture of peoples living in the territory of the Komi Republic.

The inclusion of the regional content in the basic one by means of “diffusion” and its uniform distribution in academic subjects helps to expand and deepen the main topics and sections of the basic content for bilingual students. The study of educational material based on the specifics of the Komi Republic in a multicultural environment increases the effectiveness of training. The questions of the ethnocultural component are considered when studying the disciplines of the compulsory part and the part of the curriculum formed by the participants of educational relations. In order to create the conditions for students to realize the academic law to choose optional disciplines (modules), students are offered the following optional disciplines of an ethnocultural orientation: Historical and cultural studies, History of the Komi Republic, Traditional culture of the Komi Republic, Culture of Finno-Ugric peoples, Ethnographic tourism.

3. In order to implement the leading activities of schoolchildren: cognitive, research, emotional-value, practical, control and evaluation in the study of methodological disciplines, it is necessary to use a variety of methods, techniques and forms that will further contribute to the ethnocultural education of students in a bilingual environment, putting them in the position of active participants:

- modeling (for example, performing tasks on modeling teacher's actions aimed at creating a multicultural space in the classroom: holding national holidays with parents; creating a classroom corner “My Family Traditions”; creating school communities of the regions of the Komi Republic; developing a calendar of national and cultural events of the Komi Republic, etc.);

- observation (observation of objects of animate and inanimate nature in laboratory and natural conditions; observation of human labor activity; maintaining the "Diary of the Nature of the Komi Republic", "The Reader's Diary on the Literature of the Komi Republic", etc.);
- development of the content of quizzes, contests and their conduct (for example, the quiz "The Land I live in", "Culinary Battle", "Komi mu on my palm", the contest of multimedia projects "Cloudberry", etc.);
- creation of thematic albums and exhibitions (for example, an exhibition of creative, educational and methodical textbooks "Ethnosolyanka", thematic albums "Copybooks on the paintings of the Komi Republic", etc.);
- research assignments on the topics "Komi nicknames and street names", "Tourist-local historic trails of my district", "History of my village", etc.

4. The use of various forms of organizing the activity of ethnocultural education in a multicultural space allows us to increase the motivation to learn non-native languages, in our case the Komi language - the state language of the Komi Republic. These are such forms as lessons in the classroom, matinees, excursions, walks, correspondence trips, visits to museums and exhibitions, participation in urban and rural folk festivals, which provide collective, group and individual work of students and allow to create an emotionally positive atmosphere, trustful dialogue between the teacher and students, between the students themselves. Therefore, when preparing future teachers for professional activities in the bilingual environment in the process of studying at a university, it is necessary to include the above-mentioned forms in the educational process.

II. Information and methodical conditions:

"The teacher now not only conveys information, but becomes an intermediary and partner in the learning process. Ubiquitous digitalization brings changes to all spheres of human life and confronts today and tomorrow's students with previously unimaginable tasks and opportunities. ... Modern young people have long been enthusiastically using new gadgets as interactive and exciting learning tools".

When teaching students, we suggest them to master the technology of developing elements of a digital educational environment when studying the cultural heritage of the Komi people: linguistic and artistic in the bilingual space, which will allow such aspects of education as "digitalization of education", multicultural and ethnocultural factors of education to be combined:

- ✓ virtual school museums and excursions (“Virtual School Ethnographic Museum” in the Panotour program, “Zoological Museum of Syktyvkar University” on the IZI Travel platform, virtual excursions “Monuments of Syktyvkar Architecture”, “Monuments of Syktyvkar”, “Walk around Syktyvkar as a hometown. Monuments”, “Weekend excursion”, “Walk through the buildings of Syktyvkar State University” on the IZI Travel platform, etc.);
- ✓ electronic textbooks for school learners in different subject areas using SMART technology (Electronic textbook of the Komi language as non-native using SMART technology (based on the materials from the textbook by Terentyeva, Vyazova, and Sizova “Komi Language” (2016), Grade 1”), an electronic educational resource using the SMART technology “Copybooks on the paintings of the Komi Republic”, etc.);
- ✓ intellectual, board and outdoor games with various subject contents (the didactic game “The Red Book of the Komi Republic”; folding books “Anbur”; dominoes “Traditional Komi costume”, “Komi passes”; puzzle “Republic of Komi”; cubes “Komi writers and poets of the Republic of Komi ”, etc.);
- ✓ animated cartoons (for example, "The Tale of Three Pots" in Windows Movie Maker, etc.)

III. Research and methodical conditions:

- ✓ The organization of students’ participation in seminars, webinars, republican conferences and forums with the aim of gaining professional experience in the implementation of pedagogical work in a multicultural environment (participation of the student community in the work of methodical associations of primary school teachers, Komi language and literature teachers, teachers of fine art and technology).
- ✓ The students’ master classes development and their conducting in a focus group at a university and school (for example, as part of the on-site methodological seminars “Modern Rural School” for elementary school teachers, conducting master classes on topics “The usage of interactive technologies at Komi language lessons”, “What the Mezensky Painting Tells About,” Quiz for Junior Schoolchildren on local history and ethnocultural content “My Hometown”).

The development of full life cycle projects within the framework of final qualification works (for example, the theme of the projects “Information and methodical support of the Komi language textbook using SMART technology based on the materials of the textbook by Terentyeva, Vyazova, and Sizova “Komi Language. Grade 1.” (2016), “Historical commentary at the Komi language lessons as a way to introduce students to the lexical meaning of the word”, “Information and methodical support of the painting album of the Republic of Komi” using SMART - technology, etc.

Discussions

The study of scientific and methodical sources allows to state that in the works of Prokusheva & Polyakova (2010), Terentyeva et al. (2016), Yakubiv et al. (2016), attention is paid to the problem of the formation of primary schoolchildren ethnocultural competence in a bilingual environment. However, the issues of training future teachers are not adequately covered. In our opinion, the experience of using pedagogical conditions in the framework of the implementation of the university basic educational programs in preparing future primary school teachers, which we have described, will allow them to form their ethnocultural competence in a multicultural educational space.

Conclusion

The educational and methodical, information and methodical and research and methodical conditions described in the article, implemented at the Department of Primary Education of the Institute of Pedagogy and Psychology “SSU named after Pitirim Sorokin”, allow forming the ethnocultural competence of future primary school teachers to work in the bilingual environment of the Komi Republic educational institutions. This fully meets the requirements of the Federal state educational standard of higher education - bachelor's degree in the direction of training 44.03.01 Pedagogical education (Ministry of Education and Science of the Russian Federation, 2018) and 44.03.02 Psychological and pedagogical education (Ministry of Education and Science of the Russian Federation, 2015).

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